

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part XIII. Stoichiometric Studies on the Decomposition of Hg(II) chelate of N-Benzenesulphonyl (dl) α -Alanine with Hydrochloric Acid

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Mercury(II) is known to form water-soluble chelates of the type $M_2Hg(R)_2$ with *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycines (RH_2) where $M^+ = Na^+$ or K^+ . When an aqueous solution of $M_2Hg(R)_2$ is treated with chloride, bromide or iodide, it decomposes with liberation of alkali which has been shown to be quantitative in presence of excess iodide, represented by the equation (1) and has been utilised for the estimation of Hg(II) acid-imetrically^{3,4}. With dil. HNO_3 or $HClO_4$ decomposition begins with the precipitation of $[Hg(RH)(OH)(H_2O)]$.

But when treated with dil. HCl, precipitate appeared would rapidly go into solution on stirring. Therefore it is worthwhile to study the reaction between $Hg(R)_2^{2-}$ and HCl by physicochemical methods. With this in view the stoichiometry of the reaction steps has been determined by mole-ratio method⁵ and Job's method of continuous variation⁶ employing conductance as the index property. Results show that the reaction steps may be represented by the following equations :

For the study, the compound $Na_2Hg(R_b^2)_2$ has been chosen as the representative one (where $R_b^2H_2 = N$ -benzenesulphonyl (dl) α -alanine).

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of either A.R. quality or properly purified. Solutions were made with conductivity water. $Na_2Hg(R_b^2)_2$ was prepared following the method described in a previous communication².

Conductance measurements were made with a Phillips RCL Bridge PP9030.

Conductance measurements of $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_b^{\ominus})_2$ solution at infinite dilution show it to be a 2 : 1 electrolyte λ_{∞} from λ_v at any dilution was calculated using Walden's formula⁷ $\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_v(1 + n_1 n_2 0.692 v^{-1})$ where n_1 and n_2 are the charges of the cation and anion. Data are shown in Table 1.

Mole-ratio method : Conductometric titrations were performed by titrating a 50 ml solution containing known amount of $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_b^{\ominus})_2$ with a standard HCl solution at a temperature $32^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. Similar blank titrations were also made. Conductance values after volume corrections were recorded. Now the differences between the conductance values calculated assuming no chemical reaction and the observed values were plotted against mole-ratios (Fig. 1). Results show that there are three reaction steps in the mole-ratios 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4.

TABLE 1

Conductance data of $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_b^{\ominus})_2$ solution
Cell Constant = 0.65; Temperature = 31°

Concentration	Obs. Resistance in ohms	Equivalent Conductance in ohms ⁻¹ cm ² (λ_v)	Calculated (λ_{∞})
N/16	120	86.5	117
N/32	220	94.5	118
N/64	410	102.5	120
N/128	780	106.5	120
N/256	1500	110.9	120
N/512	2950	113.0	120

Job's method of continuous variation: Equimolar solutions of $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_b^\alpha)_2$ and HCl were mixed in varying proportions so that the final volume of the species together remained constant (50 ml). Conductance of these mixtures as well as individual species were measured at $32^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. As before differences between the values were plotted against the composition of the solutions (Fig. 2) showing only one step (1 : 2). Job's method is not generally applicable where more than one step exists. In such cases following the principle laid down by

Fig. 2.

Vosburgh and Cooper⁸, the existence of another step (1 : 4) was detected. Assuming the reaction step 1 : 2 to be complete, the observed conductance at the composition 0.67 (Fig. 2), may be regarded as calculated value for studies at higher compositions. The differences between the observed values and those calculated assuming completion of the step 1 : 2 were plotted against composition of the solutions (Fig. 3).

DISCUSSION

In the decomposition of $\text{Hg}(\text{R}_b^\alpha)_2^{2-}$ with HCl , there are three reaction steps as indicated by mole-ratio method. But Job's method shows one reaction step *i.e.*, 1 : 2. When there are more than one step, Job's method may be applicable as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper using colour as the index property. Now attempts have been made to utilise conductance following the same principle *i.e.*, at the composition 0.67, the observed conductance

may be regarded as calculated value for studies at higher composition. In this way the existence of the step 1 : 4 has been detected. But the step 1 : 3 could not be found, this may be due to differences not very appreciable. However the virtual decomposition of Hg(II) chelates is the first step (1 : 2) and represented by the equation (2).

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